

THE PROJECT METHOD AS A WAY OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT WORK

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Abstract:

The main task of secondary vocational education is to form a creative personality of a specialist capable of self-realization, self-development and innovation. The solution to this problem is hardly possible only by transferring knowledge in a finished form from teacher to student.

Key words: independent work, cognitive and practical problems, classroom studies, pedagogical conditions, the ability to identify problems, collect information, observe, conduct an experiment, analyze, build hypotheses, generalize.

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With the transition to the FSES SPE, the number of hours of classroom studies has significantly decreased and the number of hours allocated for independent work has increased. Why is such close attention directed specifically to this type of educational work, and why are the skills obtained as a result of this type of activity valued more than those obtained in a training session conducted by a teacher? In order to fully understand this issue, I propose to consider what is meant by the concept of independent work.

Independent work (as a didactic form of education) is a system of organizing pedagogical conditions that ensure the management of students' learning activities that take place in the absence of a teacher and without his direct participation and assistance. The teacher's assistance is realized indirectly through the special organization of all components of the training system in conditions of self-preparation. The teacher's role is to organize independent work in order to acquire general and professional competencies by the student.

The role of the student is to turn into a creative person in the process of independent work under the guidance of a teacher, capable of independently acquiring knowledge, skills and possession, formulating a problem and finding the best way to solve it.

From the above, we can conclude that independent work, on the one hand, is aimed at the formation of general and professional competencies, on the other hand, the student has the opportunity to choose a personal educational trajectory that optimally meets the needs of the student and includes the search and selection of information, the ability to analyze, put forward and evaluate hypotheses, lead your own projects. One of the ways to effectively organize students' independent activities is the project method, since project-based teaching is the pedagogical technology that, to a greater extent than many others, meets the conditions for organizing independent work. The goal of project-based learning is to create an environment in which students:

- independently and willingly acquire the missing knowledge from various sources;
- learn to use the acquired knowledge to solve cognitive and practical problems;

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acquire communication skills by working in various groups; develop their research skills (the ability to identify problems, collect information, observe, conduct an experiment, analyze, build hypotheses, generalize);

develop systems thinking. On the basis of the Federal State Educational Standards, professional modules have been developed that determine the professional and general competencies of graduates.

A module is a relatively independent (logically completed) part of the educational program, which is responsible for the formation of a certain competence or a group of related competencies. The result of mastering the program of the professional module is the mastery of a certain type of professional activity by students, including professional (PC) and general (GC) competencies.

Professional competence is an integral professional and personal characteristic of a graduate, which determines his readiness and ability to perform professional functions in accordance with accepted norms and standards. In the learning process, it is necessary to systematically excite, develop and strengthen the cognitive interest of students both as an important motive for learning, and as a persistent personality trait, and as a powerful means of increasing the effectiveness of teaching and upbringing.

Technology of mechanical engineering, students must use computer-aided design systems for technological processes of processing parts, search and use information necessary for the effective performance of professional tasks, professional and personal development, work in a team and team, communicate effectively with colleagues, management, by consumers. The project method is most appropriate in this case. Let's consider the practical application of the project method in the organization of independent work of students in the study of PM. 01 Development of technological processes for the manufacture of machine parts.

- The main stages of project learning:
- Planning;
- Analytical stage;
- Technological stage (generalization of information);

Presentation of the results of work on the project (presentation). Project planning begins with brainstorming. Putting forward primary ideas based on existing knowledge and resolving controversial issues. Then the project topics proposed by the students are brought up for discussion. Each project participant chooses a sub-topic for future research. Thus, groups are formed, working on one sub-topic. The task of the teacher at this stage is to make sure that students with different levels of knowledge, creative potential, different inclinations and interests work in each group that is created.

At the beginning of the study of the PM. 01 The development of technological processes for the manufacture of machine parts for students is set a goal: at the end of the study, students must complete a course project. Development of a technological process for machining a "shaft" type part under conditions of mass production, for this it is necessary to collect the appropriate documentation:

- Develop a technological process.
- Create an explanatory note.
- Execute project drawing.
- Make a presentation of your project.

Students are informed that to create each document, they need to master the following applied software products: to create an explanatory note, they need a text editor, for technological documentation, they need to master the T-Flex "Technology" program, in order to complete the project drawing they need to master the program T-Flex-CAD 2 and

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T-Flex-CAD 3, and finally they need a multimedia presentation software to protect their project. Project planning begins with brainstorming. Students are divided into groups of 2-3 people. Each group will work on their own project, but each student will have their own project.

• At the analytical stage of independent research, obtaining and analyzing information, each student:

• Clarifies and formulates his own task, based on the goal of the project as a whole and the task of his group in particular;

• Seeks and collects information, taking into account:

• Own experience;

The result of the exchange of information with other students and teachers;

Information obtained from special literature, the Internet, etc ; Analyzes and interprets the received data. At the same stage, the team members need to agree on the distribution of work and forms of control over the work on the project.

Sequence of work:

• Clarification and formulation of tasks.

• Search and collection of information.

Working on a project, students in the classroom and out-of-class select information, search for specialized information on the Internet, contact teachers leading special disciplines, analyze and process the information received.

Stage III - At the technological (generalization of information) stage, the structuring of the information received and the integration of the acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities are carried out.

• Students:

• Systematize the received data;

• Combine the information received by each group into a single whole;

• Build a general logic of conclusions to summarize.

The teacher needs to ensure that students exchange knowledge and skills gained in the process of various types of work with information. All the necessary activities at this stage should be aimed at summarizing the information, conclusions and ideas of each group. Students must know the order, forms and generally accepted standards for presenting the information received (correct writing of a synopsis, resume, abstract, order of presentation at a conference, etc.). And at this stage, the teacher must provide students with maximum independence in choosing the forms of presentation of the project results, support those that will enable each student to reveal their creative potential. The process of generalizing information is also important because each of the project participants, as it were, "passes through themselves" the knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired by the whole group, since in any case he will have to participate in the presentation of the project results. Presentation of the results of work and defense of the project (presentation). At this stage, students comprehend the data obtained and the ways to achieve the result; discuss and prepare the final presentation of the results of the work on the project.

When working on a project, the teacher should not forget that the main criteria for success are joy and a sense of satisfaction for all its participants from the realization of their own achievements and acquired skills.

Students gather together all the information and make a presentation of their project. The project is defended, to which teachers of special disciplines are invited. Summing up the results of the work, I would like to note that the project-based teaching method increases the efficiency of students' independent work. Students' level of independence,

organizational and informational skills increase, the degree of interest in the studied specialty increases and prepares students for the final qualifying work.

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